

Efficient and High-Fidelity Simulation of the AP1000 Benchmark with the Fission Response Function-Based FLASH Code

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ABSTRACT

FLASH, based on the Fission Response Function (FRF) theory, is a high-fidelity and low-cost adaptive neutronics code. In this study, FLASH is validated for the AP1000 pressurized water reactor(PWR) under hot zero power (HZP) condition. The AP1000 features a highly heterogeneous core with enrichment zoning and the use of WABA and IFBA rods. To accurately simulate the reactor core, an FRF database comprising 20 distinct assembly types was constructed, and environmental factors were introduced to account for localized effects. Compared with Monte Carlo reference results, the FLASH 3D full-core calculation yielded a k_{eff} deviation of 236 pcm and a 0.99% root mean square error(RMSE) in the pin-wise fission rate distribution. The entire core simulation was completed in around 1 minute, demonstrating both high accuracy and exceptional computational efficiency.

Keywords: Fission Response Function Method, AP1000, Monte Carlo, Lattice-Core Calculation

1. INTRODUCTION

Neutronics calculations are fundamental to reactor physics [1], typically using either stochastic or deterministic approaches. The stochastic method, also known as the Monte Carlo method, tracks individual particles and is the reference for accuracy [2], but its high computational cost limits its practical use. To improve efficiency, deterministic methods were developed in one-step and two-step forms. While one-step methods are detailed, the two-step (lattice-core) approach offers a significant time advantage and remains the industry standard. This approach involves a lattice step to generate few-group constants through homogenization, followed by a core step to solve the diffusion or transport equations [3].

As a new type of two-step approach, the FRF method solves the transport equations by using fission response functions. Recently, this method was validated using the simplified, zero-burnup BEAVRS benchmark, achieving full-core transport calculations within one minute on 20 parallel cores. Compared with the Monte Carlo reference results from Serpent, the deviation in k_{eff} was only 25 pcm, and the RMSE of the 3D pin-wise power distribution was below 2.2% [4]. These results clearly demonstrate that the FRF method provides both high accuracy and computational efficiency for neutronics calculations in simplified PWR models.

FLASH is a high-fidelity neutron transport code based on the FRF method[5]. Its computational framework follows the traditional two-step paradigm, consisting of lattice database generation and core calculation[5]. FLASH utilizes three distinct databases: fission response, inter-assembly environmental factor(IaEF), and reflector environmental factor(REF). Specifically, the fission response database is constructed from assembly transport calculations without homogenization, thereby preserving explicit fission relationships among fuel rods. To account for the heterogeneous environment in a real core,

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where \mathbf{FR} is the core fission-rate vector, \mathbf{FM} is the fission matrix, k is effective multiplication factor, and $\mathbf{FM}_{i,j}$ denotes the element located at the i -th row and j -th column.

2.1. AP1000 Fission Response Function Database Calculation

The general theoretical framework for constructing the FRF database is described in [7] and this work mainly focuses on the database generation for the AP1000 reactor. In the AP1000 reactor core, the presence of axial enrichment zoning and discrete WABAs requires an axial discretization of the 3D full-core geometry. The active core height of 168 inches is divided into seven axial slices, as shown in Figure 2, within which a total of 20 distinct assembly types (cases) are identified. Independent Monte Carlo fixed-source calculations were performed for all 20 cases using a finite-height 15×15 assembly model. Exploiting the inherent 1/8 symmetry of the AP1000 assemblies, simulations were restricted to one-eighth of the central assembly. In each case, a fission source was sequentially placed at the axial center of every fuel rod within the symmetric segment, and fission rates were tallied throughout the radial geometry and at planes ± 25 inches from the center. Each case required 39 individual fixed-source simulations, with approximately 4 million particles per run over 100 batches. The complete FRF database for all 20 cases was generated in about 25 minutes using 64-core parallel computing. It should be noted that, however, this modeling approach does not fully account for environmental effects between different assembly types, which require further correction as discussed in the following subsection.

Figure 2. AP1000 Axial Slices Segment[6]

2.2. AP1000 Inter-assembly Environmental Factor Calculation

Based on the actual core configuration, FLASH retrieves the FRF database generated in the previous subsection and constructs an approximate fission matrix \mathbf{FM}^∞ , according to the local assembly type. However, for fuel rods located near interfaces between different assembly types or close to the reflector, the actual fission response deviates from the database prediction due to perturbations introduced by heterogeneous neighboring environments.

To address this deviation, the IaEF is introduced in [8] is employed, which is defined as the ratio of the FR in the real-core configuration to that in the corresponding database model. In this work, an optimized geometric treatment is implemented to enhance computational efficiency while maintaining the required accuracy. With this correction, the refined fission matrix \mathbf{FM}^∞ can be estimated as:

$$\mathbf{FM} \approx \mathbf{EF}_{ass} \mathbf{EF}_{refl} \mathbf{FM}^\infty \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{EF}_{ass} and \mathbf{EF}_{refl} are diagonal matrices.

The IaEF for a base assembly affected by multiple neighboring assemblies is decomposed into individual perturbations, each caused by a single neighboring assembly type. The overall IaEF is calculated as the multiplicative combination of the individual perturbation factors. Neighboring assemblies are categorized as adjacent or diagonal, and therefore a 2×2 assembly configuration is selected as the computational geometry.

For each perturbation, two fixed-source simulations with a uniform fission source are conducted, and the IaEF is defined as:

$$\mathbf{EF}_{ass} = \mathbf{FR}_{Real,inter-ass} \oslash \mathbf{FR}_{Database,inter-ass} \quad (4)$$

where \oslash denotes element-wise division. The Figure 3 shows the geometry model of IaEF calculation.

Figure 3. Geometry of Inter-assembly Environmental Factor Calculation

For the AP1000, IaEFs are computed for each axial slice in the radial direction. Axial perturbations were found to be negligible. In the fourth axial slice (core mid-plane), there are 22 adjacent and 20 diagonal perturbation types. Since each perturbation requires two fixed-source simulations, 84 simulations were performed using 500 million particles over 100 batches. With 64-core parallel computing, the IaEF database was generated within eight hours.

2.3. AP1000 Reflector Environmental Factor Calculation

Similar to the IaEF, fuel rods located near the reactor reflector are affected by perturbations from surrounding non-fuel regions, such as the reflector, baffle, and other in-core structural components. Since the neutron transport characteristics in these structural regions differ significantly from those assumed in the FRF database calculations, an additional correction factor is required to account for their influence on the nearby fuel rods.

In previous studies on small PWRs [9], whole-core criticality calculations were performed to obtain the critical fission source distribution and subsequently compute the REF across the entire core. However, full-core criticality simulations are computationally expensive. To address this limitation, a super-assembly method has been proposed that avoids full-core criticality calculations while still providing accurate REF estimation.

The super-assembly method computes the REF by considering a localized geometry near the reflector. This approach is particularly effective for configurations where multiple assembly types are adjacent to the reflector and offers improved computational efficiency. In this method, a 3×3 super-assembly model is constructed according to the actual radial layout to represent the local assembly-reflector configuration. A uniform fission source is placed only in the central assembly, since its fission rate is the quantity of interest. The REF is then obtained as the ratio of the fission rates obtained from fixed-source simulations in the real-core model and the corresponding database model.

For AP1000, there are three distinct 2D assembly layout scenarios. Analysis of the radial assembly arrangement indicates that Region 1 forms a wedge-shaped configuration with the reflector and baffle, while Region 3 exhibits two configurations: a wedge-shaped type and an adjacent-row type, as shown in Figure 4. As a result, five different super-assembly models are required, and eight fixed-source simulations must be performed to complete the radial REF calculation for the AP1000 3D full-core model. Each simulation uses 100 million particles over 100 batches. In addition, axial REF are evaluated separately for the seven regions and incorporated into the 3D full-core calculation. With 64-thread parallel computing, the entire REF database generation takes approximately 30 minutes.

Figure 4. AP1000 Reflector Environmental Factor Model by Super-assembly Method

3. RESULTS & CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a series of 2D and 3D core calculations are performed for the AP1000 reactor under HZP conditions with all control rods withdrawn. This section is organized as follows: the first subsection presents the results and error analysis of the 2D slice calculations, and the second subsection provides the corresponding results for the 3D full-core calculation. For the Monte Carlo reference calculations, the

2D full-core calculations are conducted using 10 million particles per cycle, 2000 inactive and 1000 active cycles per slice, while the 3D full-core criticality simulation uses 10 million particles per cycle, 3000 inactive and 2000 active cycles. Using 64-core parallel processing, Monte Carlo criticality simulations take 26 hours for each 2D full-core model and 75 hours for the 3D model.

3.1. 2D Calculations

Based on the axial configuration of the AP1000 core, the reactor is divided into seven axial slices, among which Slice 4 corresponds to the main fuel zone with a height of 102 inches and exhibits the highest assembly heterogeneity. The axial position and radial assembly layout of Slice 4 are shown in Figure 5a and Figure 5b. Compared with the Monte Carlo criticality reference, FLASH predicts a k_{eff} of 1.00148, resulting in a deviation of +198 pcm from the reference value of 0.99950 with a 2 pcm statistical uncertainty. The relative errors of the pin-wise and assembly-wise power distributions are illustrated in Figure 5c and Figure 5d. The pin-wise RMSE is 1.10%, while the assembly-wise RMSE is 0.61%.

Figure 5. 2D Slice 4 Layout and Power Relative Error Distribution

Based on the 2D pin-wise power error distribution, it can be observed that the fission rates of fuel rods within the core are approximately 1–3% higher than the Monte Carlo reference results, excluding the peripheral assemblies. However, in the fixed-source calculations used to generate the IaEF database, the fission source within each assembly is assumed to be uniform, whereas the actual source distribution

in the core is inherently non-uniform. This approximation introduces errors in the computed IaEFs. A potential improvement is to implement on-line pin-by-pin transport calculations for IaEF evaluation, which would better reflect the true source distribution and enhance the correction accuracy.

3.2. 3D Calculation

The radial power distribution of the 3D model is shown in Figure 6a, where the deviation in k_{eff} is 236 pcm relative to the Monte Carlo reference. The pin-wise and assembly-wise power RMSEs are 0.99% and 0.59%, respectively, as illustrated in Figure 6c and Figure 6d. In the axial direction, Figure 6b shows that the FLASH-calculated axial power distribution also agrees well with the reference criticality results.

Figure 6. AP1000-3D Calculation Power Distribution

In terms of computational efficiency, FLASH completes the 3D full-core simulation of the AP1000 in 73 seconds. The majority of the runtime is attributed to the database read-in, which require 21 seconds while running with a single thread, accounting for approximately 30% of the total simulation time. In addition to database loading, the 3D calculation for the AP1000 also includes the seven 2D slice calculations described earlier, which account for approximately an additional 30% of the total computation time. The collapse of the 3D fission matrix requires 16 seconds, the eigenvalue solution takes only 3 seconds, and the post-processing of the fission rate distribution requires 11 seconds. It is worth noting that, in our previous calculations, the eigenvalue problem was solved using the power iteration method, which typically required tens of seconds to converge. However, with the integration of the

scientific computing package SLEPc in FLASH and the use of hybrid OpenMPI/OpenMP parallel acceleration, the solution of the 3D fission matrix eigenvalue problem can now be completed within just a few seconds, significantly improving the computational efficiency of the code.

Table I. Time distribution of AP1000-3D calculation by FLASH

Task	Number of Threads	Time (s)
Database Reading	1	21
2D FM Calculations(7 Slices)	20	22
Collapse Calculations	20	16
3D Collapsed FM Calculation	20	3
Pin Power Reconstruction	1	11

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